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KEY FEATURES OF PRODUCTS AND SERVICES MEETING THE NEEDS OF CONSUMERS

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Abstract: The article focuses on the role and potential of products and services in the economy. Manufacturers' approaches to the needs of specific customers in offering products and services have been developed in suggestions and recommendations.

Keywords: Product, Service, Brand, Need, Production, Offer, Customer, Time, Quality, Price, Business, Employee, Competitiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of market relations, fierce competition, a wide selection of goods in the market, and rapid change in their nomenclature raise the following questions for firms - how the consumer perceives the created product, what are the reasons for the success or failure of the product? The need for analysis of such problems, the increase in the cost of production of new products, poses high risks associated with its creation. This requires firms to study the competitiveness of the goods they produce.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of quality has been handled together since the start of production. But its study began to receive much attention in the twentieth century. Scientists from the CIS and foreign countries have done much research in this area. These include M.M.Kans, B.V.Ivanov, V.N.Koreshkova, A.G.Shirtaladze, K.Isikava, O.P.Gudkin, B.I.Gerasimov, N.V.Zlobina, S. P.Spridonova, L.E.Basovsky, V.B.Protasov, E.A.Garbashko, I.I.Mazur, V.D.Shapiro, O.V.Aristov can be included. Scientists of our country are not left out of this problem. These include I.T. Abdukarimov and M.K. Pardaev. In their works, they dealt with the problems of improving the quality of services in the field of services, namely in the field of trade.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research, methods such as analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, cause and effect, space and time, systematic approach, traditional methods of financial and economic analysis when the relationship between result and factors are functional, economic-mathematical and statistical when the relationship between them is stochastic methods were also used.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main feature of the product (goods) and services is the satisfaction of consumer needs. The features of the product are divided into three groups according to human needs:

1. Functional (commodity, service) properties of the product that can meet the material needs;
2. Aesthetic properties of goods (shape, structure, decoration, conformity to modern methods) that can meet spiritual needs;
3. Ergonomic (Greek-working law) properties of goods that can meet social needs (ease of use and hygienic safety, safety, noise).

The product's maturity is the feature that retains the mentioned properties for a certain period. Normative and technical documents contain quality indicators that quantify the characteristics of each type of good.

Nowadays, every buyer buys the goods (products) he likes. The costs incurred by customers to purchase goods and services are divided into two parts. The key is for the manufacturer to target the needs of specific customers when offering products and services.

The price paid for the purchase of the first commodity (product).

The second is the time and cost of finding it.

For example. A new machine was purchased. Its price is the first part. The second part is costs such as finding, bringing, and installing it.

It is not enough that the product meets the requirements of the State Standard. The product must be created following the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards and norms.

The set of brand features includes the following indicators:

1. Quality.
2. Serviceability.
3. Reconciliation of prices to quality and consumer value.
4. Documents to be attached to the goods.
5. Quality of after-sales service.
6. Plenty of quality, choice.

Competitiveness is the ability to sell a product or product in a selected market. This can only be determined by comparing competitors' brands. Competitiveness is a relative concept, it clearly depends on the time of entry into the market. Observations of buyers who purchase goods and services show that when they compare goods, they are more likely to choose which product the efficiency (R) is higher than the purchase cost (S).

The competitiveness (K) of a commodity is as follows.

$$K = \frac{R \text{ (efficiency)}}{C \text{ (costs)}}$$

It is also clear from the above considerations that the products produced must be of good quality to be competitive. Our research shows that the most significant factor in the quality of products is the labor resources in the enterprise. In general, the following indicators are studied in the structure of labor factors affecting production and volume in manufacturing enterprises:

1. The extent to which the enterprise is staffed;
2. Effective use of working time;
3. Average annual labor productivity (labor productivity rate) per worker.

We analyze the structure of labor resources in production and the dynamics of its change in ASR IMKON TEXTILE LLC activities based on the data in Table 1 below. As far as we know, all employees working in the enterprise are divided into employees working in the main activity and employees working in the non-main activity. In turn, employees serving in the main activity are divided into the following categories: workers, employees, including: managers, specialists and other employees. Suppose it is sufficient to determine only the absolute difference in the number of managers, specialists and employees. In that case, the relative difference in the number of employees is also determined, considering the production growth rate.

1 - table

Analysis of the staff of “ASR IMKON TEXTILE”

Limited Liability Company

№	Staffing	Unit of measurement	2018	2019	Difference (+ :-)	2019 as a percentage of 2018
1	Including the number of employees	person	55	103	48	187.27
2	Workers	person	36	74	38	194.74
3	Servants	person	9	15	6	166.67
4	Leaders	person	2	3	1	150
5	Specialists	person	5	7	2	140
6	Technical staff	person	3	4	1	133.33

Labor factors affect all areas of enterprise activity. Due to this, it is necessary to rationally use labor factors to effectively organize the activities of enterprises and

the quality of products. The share of employees in the total number of employees in “ASR IMKON TEXTILE” LLC in 2018 amounted to 67.92%, and in 2019 - 71.84%. We can see that the total number of employees in the company increased by 87.27% compared to last year. We can certainly assess this situation positively because firstly, the company has created 48 new jobs, and secondly the products produced at the enterprise are sold quickly due to their high quality, so new employees are involved in the activities of the enterprise to increase the volume of production. In general, we can see that the number of employees increased by 94.74%, employees by 66.67%, managers by 50%, specialists by 40%, and technicians by 33.33%.

Since the company was recently established, we can see the largest number of employees is young people. The analysis data with the age structure of the staff are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2

Analysis of the age structure of the number of employees in the limited liability company “ASR IMKON TEXTILE”

№	Industrial production workers	Unit of measurement	2018	2019	Difference (+ :-)	2019 as a percentage of 2018
	The average number of employees in industrial production	person	55	103	48	187.27
1	Under 18 years old	person	-	-	-	-
2	18-24	person	21	44	23	209.52
3	25-29	person	13	25	12	192.31
4	30-39	person	8	12	4	150

5	40-49	person	6	14	8	233.33
6	50-54	person	7	8	1	114.29
7	Over 55 years old	person	-	-	-	-

The change in the age of employees in the company was as follows:

- The number of employees aged 18-24 increased from 21 in 2018 to 44 in 2019, an increase of 23 people or 109.52 percent over the previous year;
- The number of employees aged 25-29 was 13 last year, up from 25 in the reporting year, an increase of 12 in 2019 or 92.31 percent over 2018;
- We can see that the number of employees aged 30-39 increased by 4 people in the reporting year, up 150 percent from the previous year;
- The number of employees aged 40-49 was 14 in 2019 and 6 in 2018. This is almost two and a half times more than in the previous year;
- Employees aged 50-54 in 2019 increased by 14.29% compared to 2018, which is an increase of 1 person compared to the previous year.

The largest share of the total staff is 18-24 years old, 38.18% in 2018 and 42.72% in 2019. This means that in 2019, the share of employees aged 18-24, 25-29 and 40-49 increased the most in the company compared to 2018. Conversely, the proportion of employees aged 30-39 and 50-54 decreased. We can assess this situation as positive because the company was recently established, and the government of our country pays special attention to youth employment and provides many benefits to enterprises that employ young people.

It should be noted that it is necessary to establish an employment relationship that provides the employer with the necessary skilled labor force and the employee with labor, decent wages and working conditions quickly. To achieve this goal, the following issues need to be addressed:

- Reform of real labor laws to effectively allocate and use labor resources in the economy, strictly adhering to the basic rights of workers (the right to a fair wage, the right to protection from unjustified dismissal, etc.);
- Development of social partnership mechanisms at the enterprise level;
- Formation of effective mechanisms for resolving labor disputes;
- Increasing the role of individual and collective agreements governing the payment and working conditions;
- Facilitate the development of market mechanisms that continuously regulate the monthly wage of reproductive, incentive and regulatory functions;
- Improving state assistance to the unemployed;
- On the one hand, to reduce the level of occupational injuries of the employer, and occupational and work-related diseases, on the other hand, to reform the system of labor protection management by creating economic mechanisms that encourage the employee to comply with safety regulations.

One of the most important indicators of labor is wages. The efficient use of the wage bill primarily reduces the cost of a unit of output. This allows the cost of the volume of goods produced to fall. This is definitely a positive thing. Therefore, it is expedient to carry out rapid control over the use of the salary fund in enterprises.

Table 3

**Analysis of salary indicators in “ASR IMKON TEXTILE”
 Limited Liability Company**

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	2018	2019	The difference (+ :-)	2019 as a percentage of 2018
1	General Salary Fund	Soum	155464744 3.6	3535539436 ,8	1980891993, 8	227.42
2	Average salary	sum	2355526,43	2860468.8	504942.37	121.43

We can see that the expenditure of the salary fund in ASR IMKON TEXTILE LLC in 2019 increased by 227.42% compared to 2018. The main reason for this was the increase in the number of employees by 87.27% and the average monthly salary by 21.43%. The average monthly salary in 2018 amounted to 2355526.43 soums, in 2019 - 2860468.8 soums. This figure shows an average increase of 504942.37 soums compared to last year, or an increase of 21.43%.

The products have a competitive advantage due to higher quality in consumers' eyes. However, from the manufacturer's point of view, important product properties, such as labor, material and energy capacity, as well as significant differences in their design, remain on the margins, even if they are generally indifferent to consumers who purchase the following product.

An important component of the competitiveness of a product is its consumer properties and price. But the market prospects of goods depend not only on quality but also on uninterrupted production operation. The reason for the success or failure of the product may be unfavorable factors such as the advertising activities of other suppliers, their prestige, and the level of maintenance offered. However, no matter how important the non-productive aspects of the activities of ASR IMKON TEXTILE LLC are to ensure competitiveness, quality and price are the basis. We believe that if the products of ASR IMKON TEXTILE LLC are competitive, the main goal of the LLC will be to earn enough and live in market conditions.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

You can also see that in countries with developed market economies, there has been a growing focus on creating, improving and certifying product quality management systems over the years. In particular, this process is gaining momentum in the current global quarantine period, based on which the overall quality management has emerged. Such quality management is used not only in large industrial enterprises but also in medium and small enterprises.

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